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Use of Medicinal Herbs to Treat Dental Diseases in Vietnam

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Abstract:

The goal of this article is to provide an overview of common dental diseases in Vietnam and around the world. From there, analyze the causes and symptoms of oral diseases. At the same time, research and synthesis of medicinal herbs in Vietnam are used to treat dental diseases. Finally, the article proposes that prizes must take care of and improve the quality yield of medicinal herbs used to treat teeth in Vietnam.

Keywords: Dental diseases, medicinal herbs, Vietnam

1. Introduction

According to statistics, about 85% of Vietnam's population suffers from dental diseases such as tooth decay, toothache, gingivitis, bad breath, etc. Although the disease is not dangerous, it causes inconvenience in daily life and communication, affecting life. The main reason is improper hygiene to create conditions for bacteria to grow; Because people do not have the habit of going to the dentist, they only go to the dentist when they have painful symptoms of swelling and inflammation. The following are some male remedies for dental diseases.

Oral health is crucial for overall health and well-being, enabling vital daily activities. Oral health is a comprehensive concept that includes physical, psychological, emotional, and social dimensions essential to an individual's entire health and well-being. Dental problems represent one of the most prevalent illnesses globally and have proliferated swiftly, emerging as a significant epidemic in recent years. In 2022, the World Health Organization anticipated that dental disorders impact around 3.5 billion individuals globally. Tooth decay, periodontal disease, tooth loss, and malignant neoplasms of the lips and oral cavity are the most prevalent and severe oral disorders globally. These conditions encompass dental caries, abscesses, erosion, attrition, and periodontal disease. Tooth decay is a multifaceted, dynamic disease mediated by biofilms, resulting in sequential demineralization and remineralization of dental hard tissues. Tooth decay can impact the crown and contact root surfaces later in life and may manifest at any age in both primary and permanent teeth. Systemic health, economic status, lifestyle choices, age, gender, ethnic background, genetics, environmental influences, and the immunological response to the disease all affect disease progression, alongside local factors such as calculus and plaque.

Herbal extracts and their derivatives provide a cost-effective, safe, and biocompatible alternative to synthetic pharmaceuticals for addressing dental issues. According to the World Health Organization, over 75% of the global population depends on herbal plants for their basic health care needs, attributable to its notable physicochemical and therapeutic qualities. Herbal therapy can serve as an antibacterial, anti-inflammatory,

astringent, anesthetic, and anticariogenic agent in the treatment of dental problems. In dentistry, herbal therapy is employed across multiple disciplines, including oral medicine, periodontics, oral surgery, and dental restorations, utilizing diverse herbal items in varied formulations to address a range of dental issues. A diverse array of therapeutic plants and herbs, such as myrrh, bloodroot, caraway, chamomile, rosemary, thyme, aloe vera, propolis, neem, and mint, are utilized in mouthwashes, dentures, tubes of potions, and irrigators. These plants possess anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and antifungal effects. The structure of the article consists of 5 parts: In addition to the introduction, it includes an overview of dental diseases; Medicinal herbs are used to cure oral diseases; Analysis of methods of use and research of medicinal herbs in the treatment of oral diseases; results and conclusions.

2. Dental diseases

2.1. Mouth ulcers

Mouth ulcers frequently induce intense pain and necessitate medical intervention. Causes include traumatic injury, autoimmune diseases, gastrointestinal disorders, rheumatism, hematological issues, viral processes, and other ailments. Mouth ulcers induced by Mycobacterium tuberculosis and Treponema pallidum infections are more prevalent among individuals afflicted with HIV/AIDS or those at heightened risk, despite being uncommon in affluent nations. Patients with HIV/AIDS may also develop fungal infections, viral infections (mostly herpes virus), lymphoma, or Kaposi sarcoma lesions. Primary lesions are not blisters; rather, they are direct ulcers resulting from epithelial necrosis that penetrates the basement membrane, exposing nerve terminals and eliciting pain or discomfort. Large wounds may leave scars upon healing. Clinically, they manifest as painful ulcers with well-defined borders, which may be round or oval in shape. The necrotic base is encircled by a crimson halo indicative of hypertension and exhibits a tendency to recur. It is enveloped in a yellowish-white fibrous exudate. Aphthoid ulcers are secondary lesions, infected ulcers that originate from blisters or blister pustules. They differ from ulcers in both clinical and pathological dimensions. Other aphthoid ulcers are linked to trauma, either acutely or persistently due to recurrent mucosal injury. Some are chronic and recurrent, such as herpetic stomatitis.

2.2. Periodontal disease

Periodontal disease, often known as chronic inflammatory disease, impacts the tissues that support and encase the teeth. The initial indication of periodontal disease is gingivitis, a reversible inflammation of the periodontal soft tissues characterized by bleeding gums and edema. Gingivitis may advance to periodontitis in individuals with compromised immune systems, progressively eroding the bone that encases the teeth and sustains periodontal tissue. Periodontitis is defined by the deterioration of periodontal tissue support, the presence of a periodontal sac, gingival hemorrhage, and the reduction of alveolar bone observed in radiographic images. Periodontitis, while it may also manifest in children and adolescents, is predominantly observed in adults. Tissue loss is frequently associated with the host's defenses, the extent of dental plaque, and various risk factors. Progressive periodontitis results in substantial tooth loss and serious deterioration of supporting tissues in 10-15% of the global population. This estimate encompasses both severe invasive periodontitis and severe chronic periodontitis. Inadequate oral hygiene results in the buildup of harmful bacterial biofilms (plaque) at and beneath the gum margin, which is the primary cause of periodontal disease. Hemorrhaging during tooth brushing is the initial indication of gingivitis; discomfort is never noted. Clinical features of chronic periodontitis include the destruction of supporting tooth structures (alveolar bones and ligaments), degeneration of marginal gums (exposing the roots), increased tooth mobility and drift, bleeding in the gum sac area upon probing, and increased depth of the periodontal sac (identified using narrow-diameter probes). Acute exacerbations resulting from abscesses or dislocations caused by compromised dental support can be uncomfortable. Nonetheless, the majority of periodontal disease cases are asymptomatic, and treatment typically commences only after the condition has progressed to a severe state.

2.3. Tooth decay

A indication of tooth decay, which is a multifactorial infectious and infectious illness, is the gradual destruction of the crown and root tissue that occurs as a result of the activity of microorganisms. The primary pathogen is known to be *Streptococcus mutans*. Over the course of time, the cariogenic oral flora, also known as biofilm, creates tooth decay by its interaction with fermented carbohydrates. On the other hand, the likelihood of a person developing tooth decay is contingent upon a variety of factors, such as their immune system, their genetic predisposition, their food, the shape of their teeth, the biofilm (also known as dental plaque), the pH of their mouth, their oral hygiene, and their social standing. Bacteria in biofilms produce lactic acid as a byproduct of their process of converting carbohydrates into sugars for the purpose of obtaining energy. In the long run, this causes the pH of the plaque to decrease to levels that are dangerously low (below 5.5), which in turn initiates demineralization, which removes calcium and phosphate from the tooth structure and ultimately results in tooth decay.

2.4. Bad breath

The term "halitosis" is derived from the Latin word "halitus" (which means "breath") and the Greek word "osis" (which means "pathological process"), and it is used to describe an unpleasant odor coming from the mouth. It is also commonly referred to as "bad breath." It is a severe problem for patients because it can create social embarrassment, which can lead to isolation or, in certain situations, stigma. This is a concern that is understandable. In the course of routine checkups, it is not frequently discovered by a dentist or primary care physician, and the patient might not even be aware that it is present. Due to the growing awareness of oral hygiene in society, a growing number of individuals are seeking medical assistance in order to manage this unpleasant disease. There are a number of volatile molecules that are responsible for the sickness. These molecules include sulfur compounds, aromatic compounds, and nitrogen-containing compounds. These molecules can be created by either pathogenic or non-pathological sources. Instead of using a toothbrush, the most effective method of treatment is to use a tongue scraper. The removal of plaque and food particles from the space between the teeth is accomplished through the use of floss, which helps to avoid foul breath. According to the findings of a study, tea tree oil has the ability to effectively eliminate odors that are brought on by the bacterium *Solobacterium moorei*. Although mask toppers, such as fluoride or mint in toothpaste or flavored gum, can be useful, it is important to note that they only offer a short-term remedy. In addition to lowering the amount of onions, garlic, and spices that are ingested, it is important to encourage changes in lifestyle, such as giving up smoking, nicotine, and alcohol addiction.

2.5. Bruxism (grinding teeth)

The term "bruxism" refers to a parafunctional behavior that can take place at any time of the day or night and entails grinding one's teeth, grinding as well as bracing and grinding their teeth. When a person is awake, they may experience bruxism, which is described as the conscious clenching of their jaw. There are a number of disadvantages that can result from chronic bruxism, including pain in the jaw and facial region, the disruption of one's sleeping partner, the exposure of the inner layers of teeth as a result of enamel erosion, tooth loss, hearing loss, and temporomandibular joint disorders etc. Despite the fact that this widespread sleep issue is assumed to have a variety of reasons, a significant number of individuals have identified psychological explanations. It would suggest that bruxism is affected more severely at times of high levels of stress and anxiety.

3. Medicinal plants used to cure dental diseases in Vietnam

3.1. Toothache

Mouthwash: take one of the cards.

- Rice bark 100g, sliced with yellow stars on the ground. Pour 2 bowls of decoction thoroughly, suck this medicine for 10-15 minutes, then spit it out, suck several times a day.
- Lotus leaf root 20g, chrysanthemum root 20g. Two things of gold stars soaked in wine. Then use medicinal alcohol to dip into the cavities.

The roots of the plant are thick and colorful, gargling to cure toothache.

Oral remedies: male vulgaris 20g, earth spirit 20g, peony bone 16g, lilac 20g, dandelion 16g, dried herb 16g, honeysuckle 16g. Drink on the 1st of the month.

3.2. Inflammation around the root of the tooth

The patient has itching in the gums, around the root of the tooth is inflamed, the mucous membrane is red, slightly edematous, bad breath. Use one of the following posts:

Lesson 1: Honeysuckle 20g, fish vegetables 20g, chi zi 12g, horseradish 16g, eucalyptus 12g, licorice 10g. Drink on the 1st of the month.

Lesson 2: Vegetables 100g (gold star in the earth), rice bark 16g, hoai son 20g, lily husa 16g, flower flower 16g (star carefully). Pour 3 bowls of water to 1.5 bowls, drink 2-3 times a day.

Lesson 3: Hoai Son 20g, Son Hui 12g, Dan Bi 8g, Trach Ta 12g, Mal Mon 16g, Licorice 10g, Tran Bi 10g, Jujube 12g. Pour 3 bowls of water to 1.5 bowls, divide 2-3 times a day.

3.3. Bad breath

Mouthwash: 1 handful of incense leaves is cooked with thick water, sucked and gargled several times a day.

Oral medications:

Lesson 1: Huang Lian 12g, Huang Ba 12g, Birth Land 10g, Honeysuckle 10g, Five Spices 10g, Chen Bi 10g. Pour water into 3 bowls to 1.5 bowls, divide 2-3 times a day.

Lesson 2: 8 g of knitting, 12 g of chi zi, 16 g of ha thu o, 10 g of jujube, 12 g of white supremacy, 12 g of malt, 8 g of cadaver thread, 10 g of naked skin, 10 g of licorice. Pour 4 bowls of water, filter out the pulp to get 1.5 bowls, divide 2-3 times a day.

3.4. Gingivitis

Male remedies for root canal inflammation with aloe vera:

The active ingredients in aloe vera such as: Salicylic acid, anthraquinone, saponins, sterols... has antiseptic, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and inhibiting the activity of harmful bacteria. To cure gingivitis, you just need to take the sap of aloe vera and apply it to the area that is swollen and painful. Let stand for 3-5 minutes, then rinse your mouth with clean water. This can be done 2-3 times a day until it improves.

2. Folk remedies for root inflammation with caustic leaves:

According to oriental medicine, lotus leaves have a spicy and warm taste with 2 typical ingredients, chamomilla and beta caryophyllene, which help support anti-inflammatory and antibacterial well. To apply, you take 3-4 lotus leaves, wash them and crush them. Then add 1 pinch of salt and stir well into a paste. After brushing your teeth, you should rinse your mouth with this mixture 2-3 times a day until it improves.

(Lotus leaf is a type of vegetable, medicinal herb that supports the treatment of many oral diseases)(**)

3. Male remedies for root canal inflammation with betel nut:

Betel leaves do not have a spicy taste, are warm, and have high antibacterial ability, so they are widely used to treat dental diseases. To do this, you wash off 5-10 betel leaves. Then put it all in a pot with 1 liter of filtered water and 1 little salt. After boiling and letting it cool every day, you can use this leaf water to make a mouthwash.

4. Folk remedies for root inflammation with garlic:

Garlic is a familiar ingredient in the kitchen and is known for its high anti-inflammatory properties. To use garlic for gingivitis, you only need to puree 1-2 garlic cloves with a little water. Then use a cotton swab to dip into the solution and apply to the gums for 3-5 minutes. Finally rinse your mouth with water, you can apply this tip 3-4 times a week.

(Using garlic to cure root inflammation is an easy-to-follow folk remedy)(**)

5. Male remedy for root inflammation with guava leaves:

Guava leaves contain many ingredients such as tannins, oxalic, phosphoric, gallic acid, phenols... has an anti-inflammatory effect, effectively removing plaque on teeth. To apply this trick, you wash 4-5 young guava leaves with salt water. Take the guava leaves and puree them into a paste. After brushing your teeth, use a cotton swab to absorb this mixture evenly on the inflamed area, let it sit for 5 minutes and rinse your mouth with clean water.

6. Male remedies for ginger root inflammation:

Ginger is a medicine with a warm, spicy taste, helping to fight inflammation and effectively reduce swelling. To cure gingivitis, you should wash a small sprig of fresh ginger, add a little water and puree. Use a cotton swab to absorb the freshly ground ginger juice and apply a sufficient amount to the inflamed tooth area. This method can be done at home 2-3 times a day until it improves.

(Ginger is a medicine with high antibacterial and anti-inflammatory ability)(**)

3.5. Gingivitis with medicinal herbs

Purple incense: According to science, essential oil from incense leaves contains beneficial active ingredients such as: Ethanol, Calcium, Vitamins, Chloroform... It has the effect of inhibiting the growth of bacteria and supports the regeneration of damaged cells effectively. At the same time, it cleanses the oral cavity and relieves pain when suffering from gingivitis.

How to do: Prepare 1 handful of fresh perilla leaves, rinse with diluted salt water and drain. Boil this leaf with about 300ml of water. Use purple incense to rinse your mouth 2-3 times a day.

Lotus leaves: Lotus leaves contain ingredients such as: Bezyacetat, Beta Caryophylen,... help anti-inflammatory, reduce swelling and gradually limit the appearance of root pain.

How to do: Take 1 handful of 20 lotus leaves, 1 teaspoon of white salt, 100ml of boiled water to keep warm, blender, cotton swab, sieve. Take the lotus leaves and wash them, soak them in diluted salt water for about 5-10 minutes. Drain the leaves into pieces, then put them in a blender and mash them very finely. Mix with crushed lotus leaves 1 teaspoon of white salt and 100ml of water. Then, puree and then pour into a sieve to get the pure lotus leaf juice. Rinse your mouth with pure lotus leaf juice 3-4 times a day for the best effect.

Mint leaves have a fragrant, warm and spicy taste. In addition, the composition of peppermint contains active ingredients that help disinfect, anti-inflammatory and relieve pain very effectively.

How to do: Wash 30g of mint leaves, crush and squeeze out the juice. Take the juice mixed with 50ml of warm water, then add 1 teaspoon of white salt, stir well until the mixture dissolves. Use the mixture on a mouthwash, pay attention to keep it in your mouth for about 5 minutes before releasing it. Next, rinse your mouth with filtered water. It is recommended to apply 2 times a day to quickly eliminate bacteria that cause inflammation.

Squid grass: According to Traditional Medicine, squid grass is an herb with a sour taste and cooling properties, which is used to treat lesions caused by inflammation. Using squid grass helps to soothe pain caused by gingivitis, while also preventing ulcers from spreading to the surrounding areas.

How to do: Take 1 handful of squid grass leaves, wash, drain, 1 tablespoon of honey. Put the squid grass in a blender to puree. If you don't have a blender, you can put it in a mortar to pound. Strain the squid grass juice, add 1 tablespoon of honey to it. Use this mixture to apply to the damaged gum area 2-3 times a day.

Guava leaves: Guava leaves contain gallic acid, phenols, vitamin C,... help fight inflammation, destroy harmful plaque on teeth, protect gums.

How to do: Take 5 guava leaves, wash them, soak them in salt water for 5-10 minutes. Then remove and drain. Take guava leaves and chew them in your mouth, paying attention to keep them at the inflamed site for about 3-5 minutes. Finally, spit it out and rinse your mouth with clean water. Do it 1-2 times a day.

Aloe vera leaves: The natural chlorhexidine contained in aloe vera has the ability to remove plaque.

How to do it: Prepare some cleaned aloe vera leaves. Then cut off the outer leaf to get the gel inside. Place this aloe vera gel in your mouth and suck directly for about 30-45 seconds. Gargle thoroughly to remove aloe vera with clean water afterwards.

Yellow comb: The composition of yellow comb leaves contains many substances beneficial to oral health such as: Fatty acids, vitamins, flavonoids,... These are substances that have the effect of reducing symptoms caused by gingivitis. At the same time, it prevents dangerous complications of the disease.

How to do: Prepare 4-5 leaves of the yellow comb, wash with diluted salt water. Use a knife or scissors to cut the leaves into small strands. Brush this leaf with boiling water. Then strain this part of the water to cool. Use this water to drink daily as a type of tea, before swallowing, you should hold it in your mouth for about 1 minute.

Spinach: Spinach has cooling properties, both as a food and has a heat clearing effect, reducing swelling quite well.

How to do: Fresh spinach can be used to cook soup every day, until the gums are no longer swollen.

Chrysanthemum: Chrysanthemums have a very special use, which is to cool and purify the human body. Therefore, using crushed chrysanthemums to apply or applying the juice to the inflamed gum area will help soothe the sore gums.

How to do it: Pick a handful of fresh chrysanthemums, crush them, and squeeze out the juice to drink. Use regularly for 1 month, 2-3 times a day, or make diluted chamomile tea to drink instead of water daily, both purifying the body, reducing internal heat and effectively eliminating swelling and pain in the gums.

Lemon: Lemon is a familiar ingredient with antiseptic and anti-inflammatory properties that are both natural and easy to find. In particular, the vitamin C content in lemons also contributes to strengthening the body's immune system.

How to do it: To deal with gingivitis, you can use a mixture consisting of lemon juice mixed with a little salt. Then apply the mixture to the inflamed root area. Keep this mixture on the gum area for a few minutes to let it soak in and then rinse your mouth with clean water.

Areca nuts: The ancients passed down the folk remedy for root inflammation from the areca nuts to help disinfect, anti-inflammatory, heal ulcers and help teeth stay strong. Because the betel nut contains many pasteurizing ingredients, killing bacteria, and at the same time having a moist and tart taste.

How to do: Use a knife to peel off the green skin of the betel nut. Then, continue to peel the white pulp to the seeds. Slice the seeds in half or quarters. Put the white pulp and areca nuts and wine in a bottle, let it sit for about 1 month. When the mixture is the color of cockroach wings, use it.

Inhale before bed or 10-15 minutes after waking up, then spit it out. Leave for a while to soak the wine into the inflammation before eating or rinsing.

Ginger root: Using fresh ginger root applied directly to the inflamed area is a folk method that has been handed down by many people since ancient times. Because according to Oriental medicine, ginger has a warm, slightly spicy taste, has an extremely effective anti-inflammatory and pain-relieving effect. Using ginger for root inflammation helps to destroy harmful bacteria, prevent the growth of harmful agents, and relieve pain caused by inflammation.

How to do: Buy fresh ginger roots, wash them, scrape off all the peel and smash them. Next, apply crushed ginger to the inflamed area and leave it on for 15-20 minutes. It should be done 3-4 times a day to see the root inflammation go into remission quickly.

Garlic: Garlic contains allicin, which when oxidized, converts into alliin. This is a substance that is very good for anti-inflammatory and antibacterial.

How to make: 10 garlic, glass jar, 500ml white wine.

Use 10 peeled garlic cloves and put them in a glass jar. Then, pour 500ml of wine so that it covers the surface of the garlic and cover it tightly. Leave the mixture to soak for 15-20 days.

Take 1-2 teaspoons of garlic soaked in lozenges, rinse your mouth for 1-3 minutes.

Maintain 1-2 times a day to see the best effect.

Turmeric: Curcumin – the yellow active ingredient in turmeric starch has anti-inflammatory, anti-ulcer, antioxidant effects and enhances the recovery of painful manifestations caused by root canalitis. Therefore, turmeric starch also helps treat root inflammation extremely simply and effectively at home.

How to do: Take 2 teaspoons of turmeric starch mixed with 100ml of filtered water into a thick mixture like toothpaste. Use the above mixture to brush your teeth daily, replacing toothpaste. Use regularly 2 times a day to see the best effect.

Lemongrass root: Rinsing your mouth with lemongrass essential oil is considered a natural remedy that can help improve dental problems including gingivitis, bad breath, and tooth decay. Citral-containing lemongrass essential oil has antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant effects that help kill bacteria and fungi in the oral cavity.

How to do: Extract essential oil from rinse, dilute 2-3 drops of lemongrass essential oil with water, then use to rinse your mouth 3-4 times a day.

4. Some precious medicinal plants in Vietnam need to be preserved and replicated

Turmeric

- Introduction: Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) is a familiar plant in Vietnam, not only a popular spice but also an important medicinal herb in traditional medicine.
- Growth characteristics: Turmeric is suitable for growing in sandy land, high temperature and humidity. The tree grows well in the Central and Central Highlands regions.
- Medicinal essence: Turmeric contains the active ingredient **curcumin** which has anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, digestive support, and wound healing effects. It is also used to aid in the treatment of peptic ulcers and liver diseases.
- Meaningful roles:
 - + Turmeric is one of the most important medicinal herbs in traditional and modern medicine, with the ability to support the treatment of much different pathology. The active ingredient curcumin in turmeric helps fight inflammation, antioxidants, and reduce the risk of chronic diseases such as cancer, arthritis, and cardiovascular disease.
 - + Turmeric is also used to improve the digestive system, aid in the treatment of stomach ulcers, and heal wounds thanks to its anti-inflammatory and antibacterial properties.

- Application in practice:
 - + **Treatment of digestive diseases:** Turmeric is used in remedies for stomach ulcers, abdominal pain, and indigestion thanks to the anti-inflammatory and bile secretion stimulation of curcumin.
 - + **Supports the treatment of arthritis:** Curcumin-containing supplements are used to reduce inflammation, relieve pain for people with arthritis or inflammation-related diseases.
 - + **Treatment of liver diseases:** Turmeric has the effect of protecting the liver, supporting liver function and detoxifying the liver, and is applied in the treatment of hepatitis and fatty liver disease.
 - + **Prevention and support of cancer treatment:** Some studies show that curcumin has the ability to slow the growth of cancer cells and reduce the side effects of chemotherapy and radiation therapy.

Ngoc Linh ginseng

- Introduction: Ngoc Linh ginseng (*Panax vietnamensis*) is a rare type of ginseng, found mainly in the mountains of Ngoc Linh (Kon Tum and Quang Nam), Vietnam. This is one of the ginseng with the highest medicinal value in the world.
- Growth characteristics: develops at an altitude of 1,200 – 2,500 meters, in deep, humid forests, with thick cover. The plant needs cool temperature conditions and high humidity to grow well.
- Medicinal essence: Contains many **saponins** (more than 50 different types), along with amino **acids** and **minerals** to help promote health, fight fatigue, and support the treatment of diseases such as cancer, diabetes, and high blood pressure.
- Meaningful roles:
 - + **Potential research objects:** Ngoc Linh ginseng is the subject of many scientific studies on medicinal herbs, helping to better understand the compounds contained in ginseng and their effects on health. This opens up opportunities to develop new pharmaceutical products.
 - + **High economic value:** Ngoc Linh ginseng is one of the most valuable medicinal herbs on the market, with a selling price of up to tens of millions of VND/kg. This brings a great source of income for ginseng farmers and production enterprises.
- Application in practice
 - + **Strengthens resistance and nourishes the body:** used to help strengthen resistance, help the body fight fatigue, improve physical fitness, and promote overall health.
 - + **Supports the treatment of chronic diseases:** has the effect of supporting the treatment of diseases such as diabetes, high blood pressure, and liver diseases. Ginseng-containing products help improve liver function, regulate blood sugar, and promote heart health.
 - + **Reduce the side effects of chemotherapy and radiation therapy:** used to help patients reduce the side effects of cancer treatment, such as fatigue, loss of appetite, or immunodeficiency.
 - + **Regulate hormones and improve sleep:** helps reduce stress, regulate hormones and support good sleep, especially suitable for people who suffer from stress or insomnia.

Lilac

- Introduction: Dinh Lang (*Polyscias fruticosa*) is considered the "ginseng of the poor" due to its high medicinal value but easy to grow and popular.
- Growth characteristics: The plant is shade-loving, grows well in the tropics. The tree is about 1-2 meters high, the leaves are small, green.
- Medicinal essence: Contains a lot of **saponins, vitamins B1, B2, C** and essential **amino acids**. The plant has the effect of promoting health, boosting immunity, reducing fatigue, and supporting the treatment of diseases such as bone and joint pain, insomnia.
- Meaningful roles:

- + **Raw materials for the pharmaceutical and functional food industry:** Lingling is used as a raw material for many pharmaceutical products, functional foods and herbal teas. These products have high economic value and are widely consumed at home and abroad.
- + **Food use:** Lentil leaves can be eaten raw or cooked in soup, which helps to promote health. The leaves are also used to prepare medicinal dishes in traditional medicine, such as cooking lentil soup with chicken to promote health.
- Practical Application:
 - + **Processing into medicine:** The root and leaves of lentils are often used in folk remedies to treat many diseases such as flu, cough, arthritis, and strengthen resistance. The parts of the plant can be drunk or brewed with tea.
 - + **Milk benefits for postpartum women:** Lentil leaves are cooked into soup or processed into dishes to help increase lactation for postpartum women, helping to recover health quickly.
 - + **Aids in the treatment of neurological problems:** Lingling products help improve memory, reduce stress and anxiety, and are used for people who suffer from stress or nervous breakdown.

Green Tea Tree

- Introduction: Green tea (*Camellia sinensis*) is a popular native plant in Vietnam, which has been used for a long time in traditional medicine and daily life.
- Growth characteristics: Green tea plants grow well in high mountains, cool climate, soil with medium moisture. The Northwest region and highlands such as Thai Nguyen and Lam Dong are famous tea growing places.
- Medicinal essence: Green tea leaves contain many antioxidants such as **polyphenols, catechins, and EGCG**. They have the effect of reducing the risk of cardiovascular disease, cancer and slowing down the aging process.
- Meaningful roles:
 - + **Tea industry:** is one of the crops with high economic value, making a great contribution to the economy of many countries. Vietnam, China, India, and Japan are the world's top tea exporters.
 - + **Preserving biodiversity:** often grown in mountainous areas, helping to maintain biodiversity and protect habitats for many species of animals and plants.
 - + **Relaxation and calming:** Drinking green tea is often considered a form of relaxation, helping people calm down, reduce stress, and improve mood.
- Practical Application:
 - + **Good for the heart:** helps reduce bad cholesterol (LDL) and improves heart health. Drinking green tea regularly can reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease and stroke.
 - + **Improves brain function:** Green tea contains caffeine and L-theanine, two compounds that can improve brain function, enhance concentration, and reduce feelings of stress.
 - + **Boosts the immune system:** The ingredients in green tea, such as polyphenols and flavonoids, have the effect of boosting the immune system, helping the body fight infections.
 - + **Antioxidants:** contain many antioxidants, especially catechins, which help protect cells from free radical damage, slow down the aging process, and reduce the risk of chronic diseases.

Ginseng Tree

- Introduction: Panax ginseng is considered the "king" of medicinal herbs, famous for its health promotion and resistance enhancement.
- Growth characteristics: Ginseng prefers to live in places with loose soil, high humidity, usually grown at an altitude of 800-1500m. The growth period of ginseng is from 3 to 6 years.
- Medicinal essence: Ginseng contains many valuable compounds such as **saponins, ginsenosides, and B vitamins**, which have the effect of improving health and reducing stress.
- Meaningful roles:

- + **Object of study:** Ginseng is one of the most studied medicinal plants in modern medicine, with many research works proving its effects and benefits, opening up new directions in the development of health care products.
- + **Pharmaceutical Industry:** Ginseng is not only valuable in terms of health, but also creates high economic value, contributing to the pharmaceutical and dietary supplement industry.
- Practical Application:
 - + **Nutritional supplements:** used as a dietary supplement to replenish energy and vitamins for the body, helping users feel healthier.
 - + **Natural sedatives:** have the effect of helping to reduce feelings of stress, anxiety and fatigue, making it a good choice for people who work in stressful environments.
 - + **Protect the body:** Ginseng has the ability to enhance the activity of the immune system, helping the body fight infections and viruses, especially during epidemics.
 - + **Memory support:** improves concentration and memory, helping users work more efficiently, especially those in the elderly.

5. Conclusion

The developed medicinal herbs can help many rural and mountainous areas to eradicate hunger and reduce poverty, Vietnam is a country located in the tropical belt of monsoons, the climate has many unique and diverse features, changing from the typical tropical climate conditions in the southern lowlands, to the tropical climate of the high mountains in the Northern provinces. That natural condition has really favored the country and people of Vietnam a rich and diverse ecosystem, a great potential for medicinal plant resources in particular and medicinal resources in general. According to the results of surveys by various multidisciplinary scientific researchers, Vietnam has about 12,000 species of vascular plants (the names of 8,000 species have been identified), 600 species of fungi, 800 species of mosses and hundreds of species of large algae. In which, nearly 4,000 species of higher and lower plants are used as medicine, which are widely distributed throughout the country.

In addition, Vietnam has a long-standing ethnic medicine system with knowledge using medicinal herbs and valuable remedies used to cure common and incurable diseases, especially dental diseases. That unique traditional medicine protects the health of our nation throughout history with the motto "Male medicine treats men". If the scientific value is promoted, traditional medicine and pharmacy remedies will play an important role in protecting and caring for people's health.

Medicinal herbs in general, medicinal plants in particular exist together with the forest, agricultural and rural ecological generations, and there is a close correlation between medicinal plant biodiversity and cultural diversity, traditional medicine, associated with medical and pharmaceutical knowledge of 54 ethnic groups. is the cultural identity of the Vietnamese nation. Not to mention, the developed medicinal herbs can help many rural and mountainous areas to eradicate poverty, develop the economy, ensure social security, and protect the environment.

The planting process must comply with the right process to ensure quality. If you want medicinal plants to become a commodity, you must invest in research and cultivation on a large scale, and have a planning for planting areas. The planting process must comply with the right process to ensure quality. With the current precious medicinal plants, if they do not know how to keep and exploit without bluffing, it will lead to depletion. For example, the bitter yellow tree extracted to produce berberine has a very good antibacterial effect, treating abdominal pain and dysentery, but for a long time, Vietnam exploited it without paying attention to conservation, so it led to depletion. Now it is no longer because bitter gold is a perennial tree that must be planted for decades to be exploited. Currently, businesses that want to use bitter gold to prepare medicines have to go to Laos and Cambodia to buy...

In order to preserve and develop medicinal herbs, it is necessary to develop in the direction of producing goods to meet market demand, linking the production of raw materials with product consumption, and building areas for growing medicinal herbs. Along with that, associated with the processing industry, the product structure is

diversified to ensure safety and quality, high competitiveness, meeting the demand for domestic and export medicinal herbs. The State needs to support investment in research and application of science, technology and technology in the conservation of genetic resources, exploitation of natural medicinal herbs, cultivation and processing of medicinal herbs and medicinal products.

In addition, it is necessary to have specific solutions on the conservation and development of precious medicinal plants in each locality. In particular, focusing on developing and proposing mechanisms and policies to encourage and develop medicinal herbs in accordance with the strengths of each locality; at the same time, meeting the demand for drugs in disease prevention and treatment for the people...

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